

MULTISCALE BEHAVIOR OF LOCALLY REINFORCED COMPOSITE STRUCTURES PRODUCED BY TAILORED FIBER PLACEMENT

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Outline

- » TFP technology
- » Meso structure
- » Model setup
- » Results

Specific material properties

Normalized dense specific elastic modulus of different lightweight material

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Normalized dense specific elastic modulus of different lightweight material

Composite materials

Demands: Part mass ↓, Deformation ↓, Collapse load ↑ + Attractive design.

Possible solutions of material research: Usage of composite materials

Composite design 1.0
multi-axial

Composite design 2.0
variable-axial (VA)

Tailored Fiber Placement (TFP)

- » Development in 1990er at IPF Dresden
- » Textile near-net shape, variable-axial preform-technology
- » Fiber and base material can be arbitrary
- » Placement radii up to 5 mm
- » High reproducibility and productivity due to usage of modified industrial multi-head embroidery machines → Three IPF spin-off companies

Double lock stitch

[Source: Wikipedia]

Motivation and objective

Process parameters induce local varying mechanical and infiltration characteristics

w_s ... Stitch width

d_s ... Stich distance

TFP placement of a roving with different stitch width: formation of a gusset by displacement of the sewing thread

Motivation and objective

Development of parametric mesoscale model for use in numerical mechanical and infiltration studies

- » Obtain effective material parameters due to process:
 - » Stitch pattern undulation
 - » Stitch pattern local compression
 - » Curvature -> later
- » Get effective stiffness reduction compared to prepreg
- » Effective strength reduction
- » Establish prediction model for parameters based on stitch pattern

Meso structure

Analysis of the meso structure via micrographs of infiltrated specimen

Meso structure

Analysis of the meso structure via μ CT of dry specimen

Meso structure

Analysis of the meso structure via μ CT of dry specimen

- » Contrast thresholding to separate base material and empty air
- » Fiber / thread orientations via intensity gradient tensor
- » Thread pattern visible

Intensity gradient orientations

Base material

Sewing thread

Model setup

- » Thread displacement volume calculated by FE calculations
- » Local fiber volume content by ratio of volume before and after displacement
- » Fiber orientations via element edge orientations
- » Thread orientation via spatial description

Model setup – Fiber volume content

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Thread patterns UD only

Model setup

Fiber volume content

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Symmetric thread pattern

Model setup

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Anti-symmetric thread pattern

Model setup

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Results

Stress field - tension

Symmetric thread pattern

Results

Stress field - tension

Anti-symmetric thread pattern

Results

Stress field - tension

Random thread pattern

Results

Stress field - tension

Random thread pattern

Results

Stress field - tension

Random thread pattern

Results – Effective material properties

Refer to upcoming publication and actual presentation!

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